

A NEW APPROACH TO THE PATHOMORPHOLOGICAL DIAGNOSIS OF DYSTROPHY-DESTRUCTIVE DISEASES OF THE LUMBAR SPINE

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Relevance of the subject. It has been shown that dystrophic-degenerative diseases of the lumbar region of the spine are rare compared to other areas, and hernias of the thoracic region occur in only 1% of all intervertebral disc herniations. This disease is often observed in young and middle-aged people, the diagnosis and treatment of the disease depends on the clinical anamnestic and pathomorphology of the patients, increasing economic and social efficiency. In most cases, the hernia develops in the lower parts of the lumbar spine (VL4-5, VL5-VS1). Clinically, it manifests itself as various pathological diseases similar to the pelvis and kidney. Spine injuries and osteochondrosis are identified as the causes in most cases. Dystrophic-degenerative diseases begin in case of traumatic injury of the lumbar region of the spine, injury, displacement of the spine, and heavy and irregular loads. In the injuries of this area of the spine, cracks appear in the ring of disc fibrosis.

Key words: spine, back, joint, lumbar disc, fibrous membrane, nucleus pulposus, muscles, osteoarthritis, spondylosis, osteochondrosis.

Material and methods. As the material of this scientific research, we used the materials obtained during the surgical procedures, i.e. lumbar discectomy, laminectomy, carried out in 2019-2022 in the traumatology-orthopedic clinics of the Department of Adult Pathology and Biopsy of the Center for Pathological Anatomy of the Republic SSV. Depending on the etiopathogenetic factors, hernia of the lumbar spine can develop in 4 directions: lateral (to the side), ventral (to the front), medial (from the middle to the back), paramedial (from the middle to the side). All these species are considered highly dangerous. When this layer was stained histochemically, i.e., collagen fibers were stained with picrofuchsin, it was found that the bundle of collagen fibers was stained red to varying degrees. The fibers around the chondrocyte cells are relatively lighter, and the ones located further away from them are darker. In the dark areas, collagen fibers have joined together and formed a homogeneous substance. In the lighter stained areas, collagen fibers are sparsely distributed, torn, rhexis, and in a state of lysis. From 2 to 6 cells are identified in the bundles of chondrocyte cells located between the bundles of collagen fibers. These islets are severely

swollen, the cytoplasm of the cells in it is also in a state of severe swelling, as a result, the nuclei are in a state of karyopyknosis and karyolysis.

Summary; During the initial period of dystrophic and degenerative changes in the intervertebral disc, when the protrusion process develops in the lumbar region, pathological processes develop simultaneously in all morphofunctional parts of the disc. Degenerative changes in lumbar intervertebral disc protrusion begin at once and in different degrees in all morphofunctional parts, edema, myxomatosis, fibrous dystrophy predominates in the fibrous neck, and in the nucleus pulposus, bundles of collagen fibers change their direction due to swelling of the intervertebral disc, and the amount of elastic fibers in the content is confirmed to decrease.

Degenerative, that is, dystrophic and destructive changes in lumbar disc herniation cover all structural elements of the disc tissue, inflammatory processes are added to these changes in the fibrotic neck, as a result of which fibrous structures meet necrobiosis, crack and become dehydrated, the fibers become homogenized, necrotic, the interstitial material is swollen and calcinosis of the nucleus pulposus it is determined that it bulges out.

In the sequestered hernia of the lumbar spine, the nucleus pulposus tissue has a polymorphic structure, it is destroyed, necrotic, covered with inflammatory infiltrate and fibrous tissue, in most cases the necrosis has turned into coarse detritus without a structure, calcinosis chondromatosis and ossification processes have developed around it.

The new approach to diagnosis based on the above-mentioned pathomorphological analysis shows the high economic and social efficiency in the treatment of patients. This priority will serve as an important guide for medical professionals.

